

FLAME Policy Brief

The Importance of Fire Weather to Wildfire Management

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Satellite image (Landsat 7) of the Evros wildfire on August 22, 2023.

On this day the wildfire consumed more than 40,000 ha. The final estimated burned area according to Copernicus EMS was 93,511 ha.

The image was postprocessed by Pierre Markuse.

Executive Summary

Wildfires are a natural and recurring hazard with profound impacts on ecosystems, economies, and communities. The increasing frequency and intensity of wildfires in recent years, exacerbated by climate change, necessitate the implementation of effective wildfire management strategies. One critical aspect of wildfire management is understanding and integrating fire weather – the atmospheric conditions that influence fire spread and behavior. This policy brief, derived from the outcomes of the FLAME research project, outlines the importance of fire weather in wildfire management and current challenges related to climate change, while providing recommendations for integrating fire weather into everyday wildfire management activities in Greece.

A harsh new reality

Wildfires have become a significant environmental and socio-economic challenge globally. In regions such as the western United States, Australia, and the Mediterranean, fire seasons are becoming longer and more severe. Effective wildfire management is crucial to mitigate the adverse effects on human lives, property, and natural resources. **Fire weather plays a pivotal role** in the ignition, propagation, and intensity of wildfires, thereby affecting suppression efforts.

This **policy brief** explores the significance of fire weather, highlights current gaps in wildfire management in Greece, and provides actionable recommendations for policymakers.

Fire behaviour triangle

Source: Countryman, 1966.

GRID-Arendal/Studio Atlantis, 2021

Weather

A pervasive enabler of fire

Fire weather refers to the meteorological conditions conducive to the ignition and spread of a wildfire.

Fire weather:

- Is a pervasive enabler of fire
- Preconditions fuels
- Interacts with the topography
- Couples with the fire
- Cannot be controlled
- Gets worse with climate change.

The primary components of fire weather include:

- Temperature
- Relative humidity
- Wind (speed and direction)
- Precipitation
- Atmospheric stability

Every fire weather element can significantly impact wildfire ignition and propagation:

- **Temperature:** Higher temperatures can increase the likelihood of ignition and promote faster spread of fires by drying out vegetation and reducing fuel moisture content.
- **Relative Humidity:** Low relative humidity can lead to drier fuels, making them more susceptible to ignition and supporting more intense and uncontrollable fires.
- **Wind:** Wind is one of the most critical factors in fire behavior. It can carry embers over long distances, creating spot fires, and rapidly change the fire's spread direction and intensity.
- **Precipitation:** Precipitation can both inhibit and promote wildfires. While rain can dampen fuels and reduce fire activity, prolonged dry periods following precipitation can lead to an abundance of fine fuels, which can ignite easily.
- **Atmospheric stability:** Changes in the stability of the atmosphere have a significant impact on fire behavior by allowing the vertical transport of higher-momentum and drier air towards to the surface, as well as by controlling the potential for fire-atmosphere coupling and the development of pyroconvection.

Understanding fire weather helps fire managers predict fire behavior, allocate resources efficiently, and implement preventive measures.

Varympompi wildfire in Greece, August 2021
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Importance of Fire Weather in Wildfire Management

Effective wildfire management relies heavily on understanding and anticipating fire weather conditions. Incorporating fire weather into operational fire management offers several benefits:

- **Early Warnings:** Accurate fire weather forecasts enable early warnings of potential wildfire outbreaks.
- **Resource Allocation:** Fire weather data aid in efficient allocation of firefighting resources. By predicting high-risk areas, fire managers can strategically pre-position personnel, equipment, and aircraft to respond rapidly to emerging wildfires.
- **Public Safety and Community Preparedness:** Fire weather information is vital for public safety campaigns and community preparedness. Educating the public about fire weather and its implications assists communities in taking proactive measures to reduce fire risk.
- **Strategic Fuel Management:** Understanding fire weather conditions informs fuel management practices, such as controlled burns and vegetation clearing. These practices reduce fuel loads, thereby decreasing wildfire intensity and spread.

Case Studies Highlighting the Importance of Fire Weather

Case Study 1: The 2019 – 2020 Australian Bushfires

The 2019-2020 Australian bushfire season, also known as the "Black Summer," was one of the most devastating in the country's history. Unprecedented fire weather conditions, including record-high temperatures and prolonged drought, contributed to the severity of the bushfires. The bushfires burned approximately 18.6 million hectares, destroyed over 3,500 homes, and caused significant ecological and economic damage.

Fire weather forecasts played a **crucial role** in managing the crisis. Early warnings based on fire weather data allowed for timely evacuations and resource deployment. However, the scale of the bushfires highlighted the need for improved fire weather prediction models and more robust fire management strategies.

Case Studies Highlighting the Importance of Fire Weather

Case Study 2: The Camp Fire in California, USA (2018)

The Camp Fire, which occurred in November 2018, is the deadliest and most destructive wildfire in California's history. Extreme fire weather conditions, including strong winds and low humidity, contributed to the rapid spread of the fire, which claimed 85 lives and destroyed nearly 19,000 structures.

Accurate fire weather forecasting was instrumental in predicting the fire's behavior and guiding evacuation efforts. However, the event underscored the challenges posed by extreme fire weather and the importance of enhancing fire weather prediction capabilities to better prepare for such incidents.

Case Studies Highlighting the Importance of Fire Weather

Case Study 3: The 2021 Pyroconvective Wildfires in Greece

The August 2021 inferno in Greece was not that surprising. Analysis of fire weather data showed that, in contrast, it was the outcome of a series of events that gradually generated very high potential for the occurrence of extreme pyroconvective wildfires.

When the wildfires broke out in the first days of August, the flammability of the landscape was already extremely high since the beginning of July, while forecast guidance suggested ideal conditions for the occurrence of pyroconvection (i.e., presence of the inverted-V thermodynamic profile).

Lessons learned from the Greek 2021 pyroconvective wildfires can be summarized in the need for more efficient monitoring and forecasting of fire weather, both at the surface and within the depth of the atmosphere.

Fire is changing because we change the environment in which it occurs

Fire weather extremes in Europe have become **more frequent** in recent decades, affecting increasingly **larger areas** and **occurring earlier/later** in the fire season.

High-latitude blocking and **sub-tropical ridging** drive the occurrence of fire weather extremes in northern and southern Europe, respectively.

These trends could reverse currently stagnating or even declining trends reported for fire activity and challenge adaptation limits, while introducing fire to new regions.

Increases in the frequency and extremity of fire weather have been **globally evident** due to **climate change**, meaning that **landscapes** are primed to **burn more frequently**.

Time series of monthly extreme fire weather days for the four sub-regions of Europe, from 1980 to 2019 based on DSR95d. Figure from Giannaros and Papavasileiou, 2023 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2023.109749>)

Composites of 500 hPa geopotential height anomalies (shaded areas) and absolute values (dashed contours) on extreme fire weather days. Figure from Giannaros and Papavasileiou, 2023 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2023.109749>)

Increasing Awareness and Preparedness for Extreme Fire Weather and Behavior

Existing state-of-the-art fire weather knowledge and tools can contribute to effective wildfire management. Such approaches, among others, involve predictions of anticipated fire weather conditions across various spatiotemporal scales contributing to early warnings and ultimately increasing awareness and preparedness of all involved entities, including both practitioners and the public.

As is the case for other weather-related hazards, fire weather warnings involve predictions across the following spatiotemporal scales:

- Medium-range and synoptic-scale fire weather forecasting (e.g., via an application of the critical fire weather patterns of Greece),
- Short-range and mesoscale fire weather forecasting (e.g., via an application of the Canadian Forest Fire Weather Index System using high-resolution numerical weather prediction data over Greece),
- Rapid response fire weather and fire spread forecasting (e.g., coupled fire-atmosphere simulations - IRIS)

The critical fire weather patterns (CFWPs) of Greece.
Figure from Papavasileiou and Giannaros, 2024
(<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.171715>)

FLAME Αρχική Πληροφόρηση - Εκπαίδευση και Έρευνα - Πύλη Ενημέρωσης

Η πρόγνωση πυρομετεωρολογικής επικινδυνότητας στην Ελλάδα με μια ματιά

A 3-day forecast of FWI over Greece. Figure from <https://fireweather.eu/>

Η επικινδυνότητα εκδήλωσης και εξάπλωσης δασικών πυρκαγιών εκτιμάται με βάση το Καναδικό Σύστημα Πυρομετεωρολογικών Δείκτων (Canadian Forest Fire Weather Index System - CFFWIS), προσαρμοσμένο στο παρικό περιβάλλον της Ελλάδας. Η ανάλυση των χαρτών γίνεται καθημερινά στις 14:15 και 02:15, λαμβάνοντας υπόψη τα αντίστοιχα δεδομένα των πραγματικών στοιχείων υψηλής ανάλυσης (2 x 2 km²) του μοντέλου αριθμητικής πρόγνωσης του καιρού WRF (Weather Research and Forecasting) του Εθνικού Ινστιτούτου Ισορροπιών Ερασιμότητας Περιβάλλοντος και Βιώσιμης Ανάπτυξης (ΕΠΙΒΑ) του Εθνικού Αστεροσκοπείου Αθηνών (ΕΑΑ). Οι χάρτες αποτελούν προϊόντα του έργου IRIS.

IRIS simulation of the Schinos fire on 20.05.2021

Current **Challenges** in Fire Weather Integration in **Greece**

Despite the undebatable importance of fire weather, its integration into everyday wildfire management activities in Greece faces several **challenges**:

- **Observational Gaps:** In many regions of the country, there is a lack of comprehensive fire weather data (e.g., fire weather stations in remote locations, radar data). This gap hinders accurate modeling and prediction of wildfire behavior, as well as effective wildfire management particularly under extreme fire weather conditions. Furthermore, it is important to note the significant lack of observational data related to fuels (e.g., fuels loads, fuel moisture).
- **Interdisciplinary Coordination:** Effective wildfire management requires coordination between fire meteorologists, foresters, fire managers, ecologists, and policymakers. Disjointed efforts can lead to inefficiencies and inadequate responses to wildfire threats. Such interdisciplinary efforts are currently absent in the country.
- **Silo Mentality:** The existing silo mentality and lack of collaboration culture, as well as the gap between researchers and practitioners/decision-makers, hinders the integration of state-of-the-art knowledge, tools and models into operations, inhibiting capacity-building and science-based solutions for more effective wildfire management.

Policy Recommendation #1

Invest in Fire Weather Research and Monitoring

To improve our understanding of the processes that lead to the development of extreme fire behavior, more funding should be allocated to improve fire weather monitoring networks, including the installation of additional remote automatic weather stations (RAWS) that could be also exploited to monitor fuel conditions. Further, it is necessary to examine the possibility of using advanced remote sensing technologies (e.g., mobile weather radars, lidars) to obtain observations during active wildfires by bringing the severe weather perspective into wildfire research (i.e., fire chasing).

Policy Recommendation #2

Leverage Technology and Innovation

Encourage the development and adoption of innovative technologies for real-time fire weather monitoring, predictions and data analysis. This includes the use and further development or/and refinement of already existing fire weather prediction models/tools, artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning methods to enhance fire weather predictions and wildfire management.

Policy Recommendation #3

Understand Interdisciplinarity and Promote Interagency Collaborations

Establishing frameworks for the coordination between fire meteorologists, fire management agencies, and other relevant stakeholders can enhance the integration of fire weather data into fire management plans. This involves also the establishment of an interdisciplinary fire analysis team (task force) that could conduct real-time analysis of the expected fire behavior to support the design and implementation of safe and efficient suppression strategies.

Policy Recommendation #4

Public Awareness and Education

Implement public education campaigns to raise awareness about fire weather conditions and their implications. Providing communities with actionable information can empower them to take preventive measures and respond effectively during wildfire events.

Conclusions

- The increasing frequency and severity of wildfires underscore the critical importance of **integrating fire weather into operational wildfire management activities.**
- By understanding and anticipating fire weather conditions, policymakers and fire managers can **improve fire spread and behavior prediction, support resource allocation, and implement effective preventive measures.**
- Investing in fire weather research, promoting interagency collaboration, and leveraging innovative technologies are essential steps toward **building resilient communities and ecosystems in the face of growing wildfire threats.**
- Through these efforts, we can better protect lives, property, and natural resources from the devastating impacts of wildfires.

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